

DIFFERENCES BETWEEN TRADITIONAL AND FLIPPED CLASSROOM APPROACHES.

Dilnavoz Rakhmonova

ESL teacher at Renaissance Education University
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INTRODUCTION

Teaching and classroom instruction had been a coral issue for many years in educational areas, and different methods had been attempted and practiced throughout the history of the teaching method. Among the methods, lecture-based classes have been the most widely used in many teaching spheres. Kapur (2020) indicates that the lecture method is considered to be based on the philosophy of idealism. In this type of method, the teachers are more active during the process, and the students are passive listeners. Teacher talk time prolongs in order to provide a clear explanation to the students about a new concept. Even though the lecture-based method is still preferred by many educators and is still used in many teaching places due to its several pros, it is much more limited when compared with other methods. Kelly's (2019) findings advocate the view that the lecture method creates a non-encouraging atmosphere and is based on monotonous performance. The method does not accommodate individual needs, and because it is teacher-centered, the students get bored easily. Lecture-based methods mostly include a huge amount of information that demands the student's constant attention and leads to them taking too many notes. As a result, the students may get frustrated and confused (Kelly,2019).

According to some findings by educators, traditional ways of teaching and lecture-based classroom approaches that advocate the teacher's control and the student's silence were estimated to be insufficient, and the educational area demanded new teaching strategies and ways. According to Schmidt (2016), in traditional teaching, "I Do", "We Do" and "You Do" strategic formulations had been used for many years, and the tutors used a deductive way of teaching. On the other hand, the new flipped classroom approach involved a totally different way of delivering the classes, and "You Do", "We Do", "I Do" the strategic steps that are used during the implementation of it in the classroom. The core idea of this approach is to swap homework for classwork, and the explanation part of the lesson is sent to the students in the form of videos, a PowerPoint presentation, or reading materials. Bishop and Velger (2013) identified two activating parts of this method: it was considered a real student-centered approach, and students engaged in autonomous learning through the before-sent materials outside of the lesson. In the second part, the student's active participation in learning activities during the lesson is assessed.

Not only the flipped classroom approach but many other approaches have also replaced the traditional lecture-based method. Such as:

- Technology-based learning
- Group learning
- Individual learning

- Inquiry-based learning
- Kinesthetic learning
- Game-based learning

All the above-mentioned approaches are delicate and preferable to use in class. However, learners' engagement and active performance in them are insufficient both inside and outside of the classroom. The study intended to discover the role of the flipped approach in the students speaking skills. The study also aims to assess the student's inspiration during task achievement.

The significance of the flipped classroom approach

The main interaction of the flipped classroom approach is its beforehand delivery outside of the classroom, which typically provides an engaging atmosphere for the learners. Abdullah, Hussin, and Ismail's (2019) findings advocate the idea that the Flipped Classroom Approach can provide a comfortable atmosphere through different activities. The study also emphasizes the approach's assistance in helping the learners improve their motivation and decrease their speaking anxiety.

On the other hand, a flipped classroom approach is underlined as the most suitable and preferable approach in the 21st century, and the approach can also be coordinated with other digital technologies for increasing student engagement. Santhanasamy and Yunus (2022) identify the combination of flipped classrooms and gaming as one of the essential components for improving the students' speaking skills.

The implementation of the flipped classroom in the class demands the learners active participation in both online and offline lessons. According to Santhanasamy and Yunus(2022), active attendance during the in-class and out-of-class sessions also provides the opportunity to improve the learners speaking skills, which leads to enhancing their higher-order thinking ability.

A flipped classroom is also very convenient for the teacher because it provides a chance to create appropriate learning activities for increasing comprehensive knowledge that are aimed at maximizing learning outcomes. In accordance with its main features, flipped classroom learning can be used to teach all four integrated skills; however, its effective usage is demonstrated mostly in a speaking lesson. Because many foreign language students faced difficulties either while performing in front of a large audience or addressing their teachers. For that crucial reason, the following study will explore the importance of the flipped classroom approach to improving elementary students speaking skills.

Conceptual framework

Bennet et al. [12]

On Figure 1, the conceptual framework for the flipped classroom approach is given. The derived framework is not exactly devoted to the research work, but Bennett (et al., 2012) stated that, despite the veracity of the intended research work, they have similar frameworks. Both research works are intended to explore the flipped classroom approach, which is based on the constructivist model. Learning is estimated to be an active social process, and a student-centered environment is provided as students are allowed to use their previous experiences and knowledge for better comprehension of the new topic.

The approach might be delivered in the following order:

- short lectures on the topic are created by the teacher and posted through the online platforms.
- the students with access to an internet connection at home are sent videos; the students without an internet connection are facilitated by the teacher and allowed to watch the videos in the classroom.
- students are free to ask questions about the topic during the activity time
- if it is urged, the teacher would lecture on the further development of the misconception.
- the topic based activities have to be delivered during in-class time in order to provide students with a better understanding of the content.

In this research work, the action research method will be used in order to explore the benefits of the flipped classroom approach in enhancing the speaking skills among the elementary students.

According to its peculiarities, action research is estimated as a systematic, progressive process of meaningful investigation that is aimed at improving and identifying the problem of teaching practices. Mertler (2014) identifies this type of research as self-reflective and self-

improving, with the purpose of exploring problems. Furthermore, Dickens and Watkins (1999) action research involves four basic stages in a cyclical process. When the researchers suggested referring the problem, they first recommended reflecting on the existing problem. After reflection, a lesson plan concerning the problem has to be created for further implementation. The process of implementation will be observed by a researcher. At the end of the work, the researcher will again reflect on the accomplished procedure and what has been done in order to analyze its consequences.

(Dickens & Watkins,1999).

Current action research is being investigated, involving flipped learning in the elementary level class in order to improve their productive speaking skills. During the procedure, there will be two cycles, and the first cycle will follow the following steps:

- identifying the problem
- planning of the action
- collecting data
- analyzing the data
- modifying the theory and repeating the cycle
- reporting on the results.

The first step of the cycle is aimed at **identifying the problem** in the classroom based on speaking skills. In order to measure the students speaking capability, an oral pre-test will be conducted. There will be 10 students at L2 level in a learning center that is located in Tashkent. They will be asked to choose a piece of paper that will be put on the board, and there will be questions about different topics that are appropriate to their level. A thoughtful answer will be demanded, and the extra time will not be given. Their answers will be recoded, and they will be warned about it beforehand.

The next step is **planning the action**, which is connected to the first step. The plan for the research will be created according to the identified problem and its results. The plan will be based on the flipped classroom approach and its implementation in the classroom. The research will be conducted for three months and will be started in June and completed in August. It will last for 10 weeks; it includes two cycles, and the first cycle will last for the first five weeks while the next will be delivered the following five weeks. Each week, a topic-based module will be analyzed. There will be the same students who are mentioned above.

There will be two divisional sections to the research procedure, which are "outside" and "inside" the class. In the first section, in the outside class section, the telegram group will be

created for further processing. In order to take part in this research, students should have access to technological gadgets, and the participants' parents will be warned before the research is conducted in order to address ethical issues. The group is aimed at posting information and instructions to the participants.

There will be ten modules, and each module will be based on a new topic that involves topic vocabulary and expressions (in pdf or word format) and video-based topic explanations. The topic of the module and its materials will be posted by the teacher one or two days before, and all the materials or available sources will be posted through the telegram group. At the beginning of each module, students will have an oral challenge that is intended to explore their knowledge acquisition. Then the module will be continued with interactive activities using either paper-based or online tools, and it is estimated as an "inside" section.

The following step will be devoted to **data collection**. After finishing each module, the students will have formative assessments. The formative assessment will be based on flashcards with pictures based on the module topic, and it will depend on the right-away answer without any extra time. Each student's answer will be assessed in order to collect the data.

After collecting the data, the next step **analysis of the data** will be delivered. As the data collection will be in the form of numbers and student scores will be determined for analysis, the **quantitative method** and **descriptive statistics** will be used. The collected data will be analyzed, which will help refine the action plan if it is necessary. The analysis of the data will also encourage and modify attitudes and performances to look for during subsequent observations. By analyzing the data, the reflections on the research will be identified, and the achieved learning outcomes will be discussed. The collected data and ways of approaching problems will help organize the action plan for the next cycle.

At the next step, the theory that will have been used has to be **modified** with the help of the conclusion. After completing all topic-based modules, the students will have a post-test, which will be similar to the pre-test. Again, their answers will be recorded in order to facilitate further reflection and analysis. Both pre- and post-analysis will be compared in order to reach the final conclusion, and the methodology will be adjusted to make it more specific based on the results.

The final stage of the work will be **reflection**, in which the researcher will draw a final conclusion about the work and reflect on its analysis and synthesized outcomes. Moreover, both pre- and post-analysis will be compared in order to adjust the methodology to make it more specific based on the results. Depending on all the reflective findings, the next cycle will be planned.

Moreover, the students' perceptions of the flipped learning will also be taken into consideration, and on the last day of research, they will be asked to listen to both of their recordings in order to find out their results. They will be given a questionnaire with 5 questions on it; the questions will be related to their perceptions and findings from the research. The results from the questionnaire will also be included in a data collection so that they can be reflected on and suggestions by the students will be observed for the next cycle plan.

Data were gathered through a questionnaire focusing on the pupils perceptions of the flipped learning approach to improving their speaking skills. The questionnaire was adapted from a survey by Johnson (2013).

The second cycle will follow the same steps if the results and measurements from the first cycle are suitable for the action plan.

The results of the following study are expected to answer the research question with the desired outcomes. In particular, the research findings intend to establish a learning environment that is based on the flipped classroom approach and investigate the effectiveness of this approach in improving elementary-level students speaking skills. Within the action research, the stated problem is identified, and the cycles of the research that include purposed stages help to modify the workability of the approach. The findings from this research provide valuable insights about the feasibility of the flipped classroom approach among lower-level or younger learners. The research contributes more findings to the literature about the flipped classroom approach and its usefulness in improving L2 students speaking abilities.

There are several benefits to this work, as it is based on delivering digital tools into the classroom and is mostly focused on student-centeredness. The role of the teachers is altered from that of the instructor to that of the facilitator, and they only guide the students during the learning time. The environment of the classroom is going to be changed due to the totally different way of conducting lessons. The students' readiness for the lesson beforehand provides more time for the interactive activities, and the lessons are expected to be much more practical. The research work is estimated to be beneficial for both learners and educators; the learners can enhance their speaking and active skills, while the teachers benefit from working with digital time-saving tools. Also, the implementation of the flipped classroom approach motivates the EFL students to explore many things in terms of the language. Moreover, the students become more curious as they are allowed to work with technology.

Despite the fact that the study provides valuable insights into the flipped classroom approach, it still has some limitations. As the flipped classroom approach can only be used through technology, the attendance of educational organizations that are lacking technological devices or students that are lacking digital opportunities might be limited.

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